

IMPACT OF THE MUSIC TO MENTAL HEALTH: A LITERATURE REVIEW

OMAR ASHURBAEV

JAVOHIR JO'RAQULOV

Senior Lecturer, Millat Umidi University

Student, Millat Umidi University

javaselfdv@gmail.com

Abstract

Music is the part of life modern human being. This literature review explores how music can impact to mental health, emotional well-being and mood control. In this research such facts highlighted about music's power such as; usage of music in therapeutic sessions to cure people, mood regulations and reduce depression and anxiety. The findings shows, that music is non-invasive tool that can be used for mental health improvement.

Keywords: Emotional well-being, music therapy, neuroscience of music, therapeutic application

Aqliy salohiyatga musiqaning tasiri: Abadiyot sharhi

Omar Ashurbaev, Javohir Jo'raqulov

Katta O'qituvchi, Millat Umidi Universiteti

Talaba, Millat Umidi Universiteti

javaselfdv@gmail.com

Annotatsiya

Musiqqa rivojlangan dunyoda odam hayotining bir bulagi. Ushbu adabiyot sharhi, musiqani inson aliy salohiyati, kayfiyat o'zgarishi va his tuygulariga bo'lgan tasirni o'rganadi. O'rganish davomida musiqaning kuchi qaysiki; terapiya muolajalarida insonlarni davolash va ularning depressiya va havotirlarini kamayishini, kayfiyatni nazorat qila olishi kabi faktlar ta'kitlab o'tilgan. Topilmalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, musiqqa bu inson hayotiga havf solmaydigan balki aqliy salohiyatini yaxshiluvchi vosita.

Kalit So'zlar: Hissiyotlar nazorati, musiqqa terapiyasi, musiqqa neyrobiologiyasi, terapevtik yechim

Аннотация

Музыка превратилась частью жизни современного человека. Этот литературный обзор обобщает важность музыки в жизнь человека и ее влияние на нас. В этом обзоре приведены примеры такие как; использование музыки в терапевтических направлениях, влияние на настроение, снижение депрессии и ее начальной стадии. Существующие исследования указывают на значительный потенциал, который может быть использован в целях реабилитации и пользы ментальному здоровью человека.

Ключевые слова: эмоциональное состояние, терапия музыкой, нейропсихология музыки, терапевтические свойства.

INTRODUCTION

Music is one of the tools that serves us from past centuries, in the modern world the role of music is not only a form of expression of artists but also the tool to cure people's mental health. Many researches have been conducted on the influence of music on our mood, mental well-being and thinking abilities. This work shows the various researches about the multi functions of music and how they can affect people.

Methodology

This literature review consists of qualitative research, by analysing existing researches and refers to related articles and topics on the theme music and mental health. Academic databases were included like; PubMed, Springer and Google scholar. Relevant studies were chosen based on music's affect to human being, clinical applications and special university studies.

Analysis of Studies (Literature Review)

Neuromusicology: Understanding the impact of music on our brain

The term neuromusicology is the findings about the music's power on our brain, scientists discovered that while listening to music multiple brain regions are working. Scientists at university called NeuroImage came to opinion, which listening to a complex music can activate brain areas such as cognition, emotions and motor functions. Especially, they figured out that rhythm of the music can affect all the aspects which were stated above. Also rhythm of the music can affect to heartbeat

of human, our heartbeat is adapt to rhythm of the music. This means music has several potential ways to be used to influence our mental health.

Music and Mood Regulation

Listening music can affect to our mood regulations. Researches shows that, listening music can reduce anxiety, decrease pain and lower blood pressure, also it is stated that listening music before bad time can improve the sleeping experience. In addition to this, music has potential to use it in therapeutic ways.

Music Therapy in Clinical Settings

Music is one of the tools that can be used to improve mental health. According to Archives of Women's Mental Health, music can affect positively with, reducing anxiety and pain and decrease initial stages of depression.

In addition to this, researches claim that music therapy is beneficial with dealing dementia, Alzheimer's and cardiac issues. It is stated that by listening music, human will their brain parts to remember music, music can be associated with moments of life. By listening music people can improve cognitive functions of brain.

Self-Directed Use of Music

Individuals listen music to relief their stress or to improve their emotional regulation. It is stated that, listening music that you want can increase human' positive emotions and memories, which will cause comfort and relaxation. According to Yiren Ren a psychology researcher, listening preferred music can cause strong emotional memories related with music, which can trigger our memories. Listening to favourite songs can lead to reshaping powerful emotional experience.

Potential Negative Effects of Music

Even music has some negative sides too. While listening music with aggressive lyrics and negative songs can cause sadness and negative feelings. Also over listening loud music can cause problems to our mental health. That is why, it is important to choose music correctly, by learning the lyrics and topic of the song. Choosing right music can improve our mental health.

Neuroscientific Perspectives

Neuroscientific literature states music has power to influence to mental health. By listening music brain activity will increase, memory proceeding centres, such as amygdala and hippocampus. Music can improve emotional experience, can stimulate dopamine level, which can cause to our mood level.

Conclusion and Future Directions

This literature review states about the music's influence on mental health. Music is non-invasive tool that can be used to regulate mood, cognitive functions and emotional well-being.

Choosing right music can also lead to positive effects to our mental health, music with good lyrics and topics can lead to improve the mood and dopamine level in our body. There are also different backgrounds of the music that can affects differently to each individual, more research needed to fully discover all potential power of the music. To sum up, music influence to psychological processes by reducing anxiety and depression and improve well-being of human. Music is the powerful tool to improve mental health.

Reference list

1. Wesseldijk, L. W., Fredrik Ullén, & Mosing, M. A. (2019). The effects of playing music on mental health outcomes. *Scientific Reports*, 9(1). Nature Portfolio. Retrieved December 26, 2024, from <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41598-019-49099-9>
2. Wesseldijk, L. W., Fredrik Ullén, & Mosing, M. A. (2019). The effects of playing music on mental health outcomes. *Scientific Reports*, 9(1). Nature Portfolio. Retrieved December 26, 2024, from <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41598-019-49099-9>
- Bearman, H. (2018, October 16). Music & The Brain – How Music Affects Mood, Cognition, and Mental Health. *Natural Nootropic*. Retrieved December 26, 2024, from <https://www.naturalnootropic.com/music-and-the-brain/>
3. Rebecchini, L. (2021). Music, mental health, and immunity. *Brain Behavior & Immunity - Health*, 18, 100374–100374. Elsevier BV. Retrieved December 26, 2024, from <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2666354621001770>
4. Gustavson, D. E., Coleman, P. L., Iversen, J. R., Maes, H. H., Gordon, R. L., & Lense, M. D. (2021). Mental health and music engagement: review, framework, and guidelines for future studies. *Translational Psychiatry*, 11(1). Springer Science and Business Media LLC. Retrieved December 26, 2024, from <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41398-021-01483-8>
5. Miranda, D., Gaudreau, P., Morizot, J., Kirmayer, L., & Miranda, D. (2010). *Music and Internalizing Psychopathology 1 Running head: MUSIC AND INTERNALIZING PSYCHOPATHOLOGY Music Listening and Mental Health: Variations on Internalizing Psychopathology Last version of the manuscript when chapter submitted for publication Chapter published with the following citation*. Retrieved December 26, 2024, from https://d1wqtxts1xzle7.cloudfront.net/48011870/2012_Miranda_et_al_music